

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE REACTION BETWEEN MERCUROUS (MERCURY) AND POTASSIUM FERRICYANIDE

BY RAM SAHAI SAXENA

The reaction between mercurous nitrate and potassium ferricyanide has been studied potentiometrically, using Hg^{2+}/Hg_2^{2+} electrode. The equivalence point obtained from the maximum $\Delta E/\Delta C$ corresponds to the formation and precipitation of the compound $(Hg_2)_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$, both in the case of the direct and the inverse titrations. The titration curves have a regular form: there is a good break in potential at the equivalence point and the results are accurate and reproducible. The effect of alcohol on the end-point and on the nature of curves has been studied. The results of potentiometric titrations are in conformity with the conclusions of Saxena and Bhargav, obtained by conductance measurements.

There is hardly any reference in literature to the study of this reaction by physico-chemical methods. Whereas the reaction between $Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ has already been studied potentiometrically by Saxena and Bhatnagar (*this Journal*, 1954, 31, 157) and that between $Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ by conductivity measurements by Saxena and Bhargav (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1954, 276, 204), the present paper incorporates the study of the latter reaction by potentiometric method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents were used. The solutions of mercurous nitrate and potassium ferricyanide were standardised as described earlier (*loc. cit.*). Using different concentrations of the reactants, the potentiometric titrations were performed by the direct and the inverse methods, *i.e.* when $Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ solution from the micro-burette was added to $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ solution in the electrode vessel and *vice versa*. In either case, mercurous nitrate containing mercuric nitrate (1%) was used to make Hg^{2+}/Hg_2^{2+} electrode. A foil of platinised platinum was immersed in the titre and used as an indicator electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode by means of a KNO_3 bridge. E.M.F. was measured on a Cambridge *p_x* meter. Curves were plotted (not shown) between the volume of the titrant and the *E* observed. The equivalence point was calculated from the maximum value of $\Delta E/\Delta C$ in each case. Titrations were also carried out in presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20% by volume; 20 c.c. of the solution was taken in the cell each time.

TABLE I

Summary of results of potentiometric titrations.

$Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ or $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ required (in c.c.) for formation of $(Hg_2)_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$.

$Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ soln.	K_3FeCy_6 soln.	Calc.	Obtained from $\Delta E/\Delta C$ in presence of alcohol			$Hg_2(NO_3)_2$ soln.	K_3FeCy_6 soln.	Calc.	Obtained from $\Delta E/\Delta C$ in presence of alcohol		
			0%	10%	20%				0%	10%	20%
0.26M	0.05M	5.77	5.45	5.55	5.70	M/20	M/7.0	4.66	4.54	4.60	4.65
M/10	M/50	6.00	5.80	5.85	5.95	M/60	M/20	4.44	4.32	4.36	4.15
M/50	M/300	4.99	4.90	4.95	5.00	M/200	M/75	5.00	4.95	5.00	5.00

DISCUSSION

The potentiometric titration curves, both in the direct and the inverse titrations, yield only one break in potential corresponding to the formation and complete precipitation of the compound $(\text{Hg}_2)_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$, where the molecular ratio of the reactants, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, is 3:2. The formation of the intermediate compound $\text{KHg}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, as suggested by the results of conductometric titration (*loc. cit.*), has not been indicated by the potentiometric results.

It is clear from Table I that the observed points of equivalence (obtained from $\max. \Delta E/\Delta C$) in aqueous medium are slightly lower than those calculated for the formation of $(\text{Hg}_2)_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$ and by the addition of alcohol in increasing amounts, the observed titre values gradually approach the calculated points of equivalence.

The discrepancy between the observed and the calculated titre values in aqueous medium and the subsequent change, when the titrations are performed in alcoholic medium, support our views on the adsorptive behaviour of such ferro- and ferricyanide complexes (cf. R. S. Saxena and co-workers, previous publications). The effect of adsorption of Hg_2^{2+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ ions from the surrounding solution by the precipitated compound would be to decrease the titre values in aqueous medium in both cases which should then increase in presence of alcohol, which helps to check adsorption. This has actually been observed. The effect of adsorption is more marked in concentrated solutions than in dilute solutions.

In all titrations a brownish yellow precipitate is formed and the supernatant liquid is marked by a sharp change to a light greenish tinge just before the end-point. In direct titrations, the potential is stable from the beginning but changes greatly on each addition of mercurous nitrate, a little before the end-point, and it takes about half an hour after each addition for the potential to become steady. After the equivalence point is crossed, the potential changes in a regular manner. In the inverse titrations, however, the potential remains steady throughout. It first decreases, then begins to increase just before the end-point, which is then marked by a sharp jump. The latter titrations take a shorter time than the former. The presence of alcohol decreases the break in potential at the equivalence point in either case. The titrations give accurate and reproducible results.

From the potentiometric titrations, it can be concluded that the composition of mercurous ferricyanide is expressed by the formula $(\text{Hg}_2)_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_2$, which is in fair agreement with the results obtained from conductivity (*loc. cit.*).